

EVALUATION OF THE INCIDENCE RATE OF GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE AMONG STUDENTS USING THE GERDQ QUESTIONNAIRE

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In this study, the prevalence of gastroesophageal reflux disease among students was investigated using the GERDQ questionnaire. 50 students of the 3rd year participated in the research. The results of the tests are based on the high incidence of gastroesophageal reflux disease among young men.

Key words: gastroesophageal reflux disease, GERDQ questionnaire, heartburn, regurgitation

Purpose. Evaluation of the prevalence of gastroesophageal reflux disease among students using the GERDQ questionnaire

Materials and methods. 50 students of groups 301-303 were involved in the research.

Among the students involved in research, 20 are girls and 30 are boys, their age is around 21-24 years (average 2.4 ± 1.2). The GERDQ questionnaire expressed the points according to symptoms of heartburn, regurgitation, pain (0 times a week, 1-2 times a week, 2-3 times a week, 4-7 times a week). Taken facts are recycled used from Student's T-yardstick and diversity of $P < 0.05$ results are acknowledged as reliable.

Results and discussion. The clinical sign of boils was detected in the same way among boys and girls - 0 times a week in 64% of boys and 74% of girls, 1-2 times a week in 30%, in girls 18%, 2-3 times a week in 4% of boys and girls, and 4-7 2% were observed once a week, 4-7 times a week 2% in boys and 4% in girls. The symptoms of regurgitation and ocre sensation were also found to be higher in young men.

This slide result shows us GERD is spreaded among students but it meets mostly boys than girls. The main reason of this illness is boys` often destroy of the eating regime, they don't observe gigiena rules, they be busy with bad habits and such kind of bad things influnce to this illness